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pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com
+639985799958

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COMMITMENT, PREPARATIONS, AND PRACTICES OF SCHOOL PAPER ADVISERS

JENA ABEGAIL J. ACAYEN, LPTY, MAEd

Teacher III

*Bagong Silang Elementary School
SDO Caloocan*

ABSTRACT

Campus Journalism is considered to be the pillar of truth within the school and becomes the campus journalists' pathway for promoting school and community awareness to their fellow students.

School Paper Advisers are part of the success of campus journalism and their role is equally valuable as to the campus journalists. Their part in the success of these young journalists is as essential as anyone else, and is considered crucial to the success of the school paper. Moreso, they must hold fairness between training and giving freedom to produce a school paper that reflects the voice of the student body; must be fully committed to the responsibilities associated with it, and are expected to be part of the ways in strengthening campus journalism practice among students through preparations for trainings and participating as stipulated in Section 8 of RA 7079. The experiences of SPAs are certainly a significant factor on the competence of campus journalists during conferences.

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